

"Mirzo Ulugbek Successors" Competition and its Financing System

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Abstract: the significance of the "Mirzo Ulugbek Successors" competition and the stages of its implementation, the level of inclusion of young people in the remote areas of our country is increasing year by year through the systems of financial incentives. the level of inclusion of young people is growing, and the interest of young people in the innovative field is also increasing.

Keywords: Mirzo Ulugbek Successors, Ulugbek Foundation, innovation, competition, technology, science, achievements, scientific center, inventions, startups, engineering, science and education, youth, scientific developments, young entrepreneurs, innovative solutions, social development, funding system, financial resources, awards, scholarships, grants, financial incentives.

"Mirzo Ulugbek Successors" Republican contest "Talented youth" of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 18, 2022 support was established in order to ensure the implementation of the decision No. 30 "On measures to develop the activities of the Ulugbek Foundation" and is an annual competition with the aim of attracting young people to science and innovation.

"Mirzo Ulugbek Successors" national competition is an event held in Uzbekistan to support young people who have achieved high results in the fields of science, education, innovation and technology. The name of this pageant was inspired by the recognition of Mirzo Ulugbek's great contribution to science and culture. In his time, Ulugbek achieved great achievements in the field of science and astronomy, created a unique scientific center in Samarkand and contributed to the development of science.

The purpose of the competition:

"Mirzo Ulugbek Successors" is the main part of the republican competition.

Its purpose is to develop science, technologies, innovations, inventions and start-ups among young people, thereby developing creative thinking and creative potential of young people in Uzbekistan. Young people who have achieved high results in various fields such as technology, information and communication technologies, scientific research, engineering, science and education will participate in the competition.

The main directions of the competition:

Science and Research: New scientific developments and research presented by young scientists, research scientists and doctoral students.

Innovations and technologies: Young entrepreneurs and startups present their innovative products or technologies. Projects aimed at the development of information technologies, artificial intelligence, robotics and other advanced technologies are highly valued within this field.

Research and inventions: Young inventors present new technical inventions, innovative solutions aimed

at solving environmental problems, new scientific approaches.

Innovations in the field of education: new educational methods, online educational platforms, developments in the use of technologies in education.

Importance of the choice:

Development of science and innovation: "Mirzo Ulugbek Successors" national competition encourages and supports young people to achieve new achievements in science and technology.

Support of young people: The contest allows to introduce young people to the public with their scientific and innovative developments, and opens up new opportunities for them.

National and global success: Young people who won the competition will have the opportunity to present their achievements not only in Uzbekistan, but also internationally.

A total of 47,514 (23,811 in 2022, 43,125 in 2023) talented young people took part in the 2024 contest.

Funding system of the competition and its funds:

The 1st stage of the competition was organized in 206 districts (cities) of our Republic, where a total of 9,796 young people presented their projects to the members of the Commission. At the end of this stage, a total of 1003 talented young people from 5 regions were recognized as winners and will be encouraged in the amount of 5 times the BHM (1,700,000 soums).

The 1st stage of the competition was organized in the region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent, where a total of 1003 young people presented their projects to the members of the Commission. At the end of this stage, a total of 280 talented young people from 20 from each region were recognized as winners and were encouraged in the amount of 10 times the BHM (3,400,000 soums).

The financing system of the "Mirzo Ulugbek Successors" republican competition is usually implemented by the state agencies that organize the competition, as well as special sponsors and partner organizations. Finance of the contest.

Support often comes from the following main sources:

1. State budget and financial support:

The financial support of the competition is carried out mainly through funds allocated from the state budget, in particular, from special state programs aimed at the development of science, education and innovation. At a time when special attention is paid to the science and education sector of Uzbekistan, it is very important to support the financing of such contests by the state.

Country:

Organizational costs of the competition (management, advertising, technical support, public relations, etc.);

Prizes and scholarships (money prizes for competition winners, scholarships, grants);

It can provide grants and financial support for startups to support young inventors and entrepreneurs.

2. Private sector and sponsors:

The role of the private sector in financing the competition is also important. This includes entrepreneurs, companies, banks and other corporate organizations.

Grants and Funds: Private sector organizations and companies can provide grants or scholarships for the scientific and technological development of young people.

3. International organizations and grants:

Many international scientific-research, technological and social development organizations can

participate in the competition. Such organizations may be interested in supporting the development of advanced technologies in Uzbekistan. Some of them may be:

International organizations such as the United Nations (UN), the European Union or the World Bank;
International scientific funds and grant programs.

Additional funds for the competition can be attracted through such organizations. They are especially innovative and scientific research projects allocate grants and funds aimed at support.

4. Organizations and universities participating in the competition:

All higher education institutions, scientific institutes and innovation centers in Uzbekistan can allocate their resources to support the competition. For example, through their research centers, technological laboratories or incubation centers, participants can be provided with the infrastructure to carry out initial research and development. In addition, these organizations can demonstrate their scientific and technical potential in the competition.

5. Rewards and incentive system:

Incentive prizes, scholarships and grants are provided for the winners of the competition. Financial incentives can be in the following forms:

Cash prizes: Cash prizes for winners and young people presenting the best projects.

Grants and start-up funds: Grants or start-up capital for the implementation of research or innovation projects for winners or a number of participants.

Scholarships: Providing scholarships for studying or conducting scientific research at universities.

6. Corporate social responsibility (CSR) programs:

Some private companies may contribute to contest funding as part of their corporate social responsibility (CSR) programs. Through these programs, companies help support young people and develop their innovative and social projects.

Summary:

"Mirzo Ulugbek Successors" republican competition is a great opportunity to encourage young people to think innovatively and create new technologies. This competition will also contribute to the development of Uzbekistan's science, technology and education sectors and increase its competitiveness at the global level. The name of the competition commemorates Ulugbek's great contribution to science and culture and encourages young people to continue this legacy.

Financial support for the competition comes from many sources, including the state budget, the private sector, international organizations, universities and other scientific partners. Such a system expands the possibilities of developing the competition, supporting the winners and implementing their innovative projects.

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